

A Human-Centred Framework for Maritime Education and Training in Coastal Remote Autonomous Ship Operations

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Abstract—The current Maritime Training and Education (MET) framework, based on the International Convention on Standards of Training, Certification and Watchkeeping for Seafarers (STCW), was designed for the operation of conventional ships. In 2024, 20% of incidents involving conventional ships in Irish coastal waters were due to grounding, collision, allision, or other manoeuvring issues. This highlights the ongoing need for a revised MET framework for remote operations of Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS). Despite established training for conventional ships, incident rates remain high. Remote MASS operations pose greater risks and challenges because there is no crew on board, limiting situational awareness. To address this, a scoping review of relevant regulations, guidelines, and best practices was conducted. The review considered assumptions about MASS size, operational modes, operating areas, and work functions. Six primary and four secondary sources were identified, resulting in 24 main competencies. These competencies were mapped to the Software, Hardware, Environment, and Liveware (SHELL) model to provide a human-centric foundation for the future MET framework.

Index Terms—Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS), Maritime Training and Education (MET), scoping review, human-centred framework, SHELL model

I. INTRODUCTION

In 2017, the International Maritime Organization (IMO) formally recognised the operation of ships with advanced levels of autonomy [1]. The term Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS) was subsequently used, referring to ships capable of operating independently of human intervention at varying degrees of autonomy [2]. The degrees of autonomy are classified as follows:

- Degree one: conventional ships equipped with automated processes and decision support systems.
- Degree two: remotely controlled ship with seafarers on board.
- Degree three: remotely controlled ship without any seafarers on board.
- Degree four: fully autonomous ship, with human presence remains essential to monitor operations [3]

The current Maritime Education and Training (MET) framework is based on the International Convention on Standards

of Training, Certification and Watchkeeping for Seafarers (STCW), which was designed for conventional ships [4]. This framework is insufficient for MASS, particularly at degrees three and four, where human operators remotely control the ship. These advancements introduce regulatory challenges due to the removal of crew from onboard roles and the shift in control between human operators and autonomous systems [5].

On May 22, 2026, the IMO finalised and adopted the non-mandatory MASS Code, which will take effect on July 1, 2026 [6]. This code supplements existing IMO legal instruments by establishing a regulatory framework for MASS operations, including the identification of essential skills and competencies for MASS operators. Notably, the code functions as a goal-based instrument rather than prescribing specific technical requirements [7]. Consequently, the details of the training framework must be defined independently.

To further demonstrate the need for a revised training framework for MASS, 81 incidents involving conventional ships in Irish waters were reported in 2024. Of these, 16 incidents involved grounding, collision, allision, or other manoeuvring events, representing 20% of the total [8]. Although these statistics may not directly reflect the situation for MASS due to the absence of reported incident data, they underscore a significant concern. Conventional ship operations continue to experience a considerable proportion of incidents despite established regulations and training frameworks. The challenges associated with MASS are expected to be more significant, given reduced situational awareness. Therefore, the development of new training approaches for MASS, particularly for navigation and steering functions, is both essential and urgent, especially considering that MASS has been operating on the Irish coast since 2022 [9].

This paper presents a scoping review that serves as the foundation for developing a future MASS training framework by holistically mapping the competencies required for MASS operations using the SHELL model (Software, Hardware, Environment, and Liveware). In subsequent research, these competencies will be further delineated into knowledge (cognitive), understanding (interpretive), and proficiency (opera-

tional) components, with assessment criteria and methods to be defined [4], [10].

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Defining initial assumptions

Prior to defining the initial assumptions that constrain the training framework, the general concept of remote operation for MASS must be clarified to establish the scope. The operational process begins with the preparation and planning phase at the Shore Control Centre (SCC) and extends through the sailing phase until the MASS arrives at its designated target or location. Consequently, the training framework will encompass the entire operational sequence from initiation to completion [11]. This operational flow is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. General operational sequence of remote MASS.

The categories for initial assumptions are derived from the use-case description of the risk-assessment method developed in the AUTOSHIP project [12]. While the current IMO MASS Code is applicable exclusively to cargo and convention-sized ships [7], additional modifications are necessary to address the specific MASS operation outlined above. The initial assumptions are as follows:

- MASS size: small size, less than 24 metres [13].
- Degree of automation: IMO degrees three and four.
- Area of operation: coastal area.
- Function: navigation and steering control.

B. Scoping review

This study uses a structured scoping review with a rigorous and transparent search and selection process, based on previously defined assumptions. The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS), 1982, provides the legal basis, with the 2017 edition of STCW serving as the main framework.

Primary sources include documents from the IMO regulatory scoping exercise, which identified high-priority instruments for amendment or development, such as the International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS) and the International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea (COLREG) [2]. Goal-based guidelines specific to MASS are also considered [3], [14]. Secondary sources, such as guidelines from authorities and industry best practices, provide descriptive and technical support for the training framework. The complete list and categorisation of documents used in the scoping review are presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. List and group of documents assessed for scoping review.

C. SHELL identification

A human-centred conceptual framework, the SHELL model, is employed to organise the identified items from the scoping review. The SHELL model was first introduced as a conceptual framework for analysing human factors in aviation [15]. In this model, Liveware represents humans, whose interactions with the S-H-E-L components are systematically assessed. For this research, the SHELL elements are defined as follows:

- Software: regulations, frameworks, and operational procedures.
- Hardware: MASS and all associated systems, with particular emphasis on autonomous systems.
- Environment: the surrounding factors that influence operational activities.
- Liveware(s): behavioural markers characterising interactions between human operators and between operators and autonomous systems.

III. RESULTS

A. Scoping review

1) *Legal basis and main framework:* UNCLOS 1982 provides the foundational legal framework governing maritime activities. Its mandatory provisions regarding navigation safety, maritime traffic regulation, and the protection of the marine environment and facilities are directly applicable to MASS operations [16]. Meanwhile, the main framework for the review will refer to the most current STCW 2017, which consists of the STCW Convention 1978 and the updated STCW Code 1995, which is divided into Part A: Mandatory provisions and minimum standards and Part B: Recommended guidance.

This scoping review considers only Part A of the STCW Code, in reference to the Convention, with the following sections selected:

- Section A-1: Items regarding near-coastal voyage principles, training and assessment, quality standards, and simulator use standards.
- Section A-II: This section includes Knowledge, Understanding, and Proficiency (KUP) tables outlining minimum competency standards at operational and management levels. Relevant functional areas for MASS are navigation, operation, and control. An assessment of the KUP tables shows that 62% of operational-level and 50% of management-level requirements apply to MASS.
- Section A-VIII: This section discusses voyage planning and outlines arrangements and principles for watchkeeping.

2) *Primary and secondary sources:* The primary sources are derived from MSC.1/Circ. 1638, which evaluates International Maritime Organization (IMO) high-priority instruments for potential application to Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS). These instruments include SOLAS 1974 and COLREG 1972, as well as the previously discussed STCW. Additional IMO guidelines and circular documents are also considered. The identified items are outlined below.

- COLREG 1972: The relevant sections include Part B, which addresses the conduct of ships under all visibility conditions, including interactions between ships such as head-on, overtaking, and crossing situations, as well as operations in restricted visibility. Part D, which pertains to manoeuvring and warning signals, is also considered.
- SOLAS 1974: The analysis focuses exclusively on Chapter V, Safety of Navigation. Relevant items for MASS include danger messages, meteorological services, routing, signalling lamps, navigation, manning, radiocommunication, and the use of automatic piloting.

- MSC 110/WP.8: The assessment covers nine chapters, including MASS surveys and certification, risk assessment, operational context, management of safe operations, alert management, human element considerations, safety of navigation, remote operations, and special measures to enhance maritime security.
- MSC.1/Circ.1604: This interim guideline for MASS trials outlines principles and primary objectives, including risk management, compliance with mandatory instruments, manning qualifications, human element considerations, trial infrastructure and awareness, communication and data exchange, reporting and information sharing, trial scope and objectives, and cyber risk management.
- MSC-FAL.1/Circ.3/Rev.3: This guideline addresses maritime cyber risk management, focusing primarily on the protection of Computer-Based Systems (CBS), which encompass both Information Technology (IT) and Operational Technology (OT) as integral components of the MASS cyber system.

Secondary sources serve to complement primary sources, which are typically goal-oriented. These sources may identify additional elements overlooked during the assessment of primary sources and provide detailed technical information on the identified items. Such information is essential for subsequent steps in upgrading the STCW KUP tables.

Industrial best practices are derived from the SMI UK Voluntary Guide and AUTOSHIP project deliverables D2.4 (Risk assessments, fail-safe procedures, and acceptance criteria), D3.2 (Autonomous ship design methods and test principles), and D7.2 (Autonomous ship training framework for crew, operators, and designers). Guidelines from authorities are drawn from the Norwegian Maritime Authority Circular Series V and the UK Marine Guidance Note 703, as they are relevant to maritime operations in Irish coastal waters.

TABLE 1
SHELL MAIN COMPETENCIES FOR REMOTE MASS OPERATIONS

Software	Hardware	Environment	Liveware(s)
Familiarity with MASS terminology and modes of operation.	An understanding of the Shore Control Centre (SCC) infrastructure.	Awareness of visibility and situational factors.	Proficiency in Maritime English communication.
Clear definition of roles and responsibilities between human operators and autonomous systems.	A robust connection and cybersecurity measures.	Consideration of sea state and meteorological conditions.	Effective emotional and stress regulation.
Adherence to operational procedures and Concept of Operations (ConOps).	Expertise in autonomous systems guidance, navigation, and control.	Management of bandwidth and network latency.	Strong managerial and team coordination skills.
Understanding operational capabilities and limitations.	Effective use of situational awareness systems, such as cameras, radar, and infrared.	Assessment of traffic distribution and density.	A sound decision-making without over-reliance on the system.
Implementation of risk management procedures and compliance with regulatory instruments.	Familiarity with intelligent machinery systems.	Awareness of water depth and bathymetry.	Strong critical thinking and adaptability.
Meeting prerequisites and manning qualifications.	Understanding safety systems, including light and sound signals and override mechanisms.	Knowledge of the geographical landscape of the surrounding area.	Maintaining alertness for watchkeeping and intrusion detection.

B. SHELL identification

The scoping review demonstrated that all elements identified in the sections and chapters can be categorised according to their respective themes. These elements were then grouped into 24 common themes, derived from both primary and secondary sources, and mapped onto the SHELL model as the main competencies required for MASS operators. Each element encompasses six primary competencies. The results are summarised in Table 1.

It should be noted that the results of this scoping review represent only the initial step in identifying the main competencies. The next stage of research will involve breaking down these main competencies into KUP mapping to complement the STCW 2017 table for MASS operations.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A novel Maritime Education and Training (MET) framework is necessary to equip human operators to manage advanced technologies such as Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS), particularly in the dynamic environments of the Irish coast. Through the evaluation of primary and secondary sources, 24 competencies have been identified and systematically mapped using a holistic SHELL model, which addresses software, hardware, environment, and liveware components. This approach complements the Standards of Training, Certification, and Watchkeeping (STCW) 2017, which serves as the principal framework for MET. The identified competencies are based on an analysis of recurring themes and discussions found in legal documents, guidance, and best practices issued by regulatory bodies such as the International Maritime Organization (IMO), national authorities, and the maritime industry. However, additional work is needed to further develop these competencies into specific knowledge, understanding, and proficiency items to be assessed as part of the complete MET framework.

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REFERENCES

- [1] IMO, "Maritime autonomous surface ships; proposal for a regulatory scoping exercise," MSC 98/20/2, Feb. 2017.
- [2] IMO, "Outcome of the regulatory scoping exercise for the use of maritime autonomous surface ships (mass)," MSC.1/Circ.1638, Jun. 2021.
- [3] IMO, "Development of a goal-based instrument for maritime autonomous surface ships (mass)," MSC 110/WP.8, Aug. 2025.
- [4] IMO, *Standards of Training, Certification and Watchkeeping for Seafarers (STCW) 2017 Edition*. International Maritime Organization, 2018, ISBN: 9789280116359.
- [5] E. R. Lange, *Regulating Autonomous Vessel: International, Regional, and European Regulation of Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships*. Brill/Nijhoff, 2025, vol. 103, ISBN: 978-90-04-72947-6.
- [6] DNV, *Imo msc 111: New mass code adopted*, May 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.dnv.com/news/2026/imo-mcs-111-new-mass-code-adopted/>.
- [7] IMO, "Development of a goal-based instrument for maritime autonomous surface ships (mass): Comments for consideration in the finalization of the mass code," MSC 111/5/5, Feb. 2026.
- [8] MCIB, "Mcib 2024 incidents & investigations," Marine Casualty Investigation Board, Tech. Rep., 2025. [Online]. Available: https://www.maiu.gov.ie/assets/files/pdf/mcib_incidents_investigations_report_2024.pdf.
- [9] A. Habibic, *Xocean in ireland's first uncrewed vessel survey*, Feb. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.offshore-energy.biz/xocean-in-irelands-first-unmanned-vessel-survey/>.
- [10] M. H. Dewan, M. A. A. Mustafi, F. Matos, and R. Godina, "Exploring seafarers' knowledge, understanding, and proficiency in seemp: A strategic training framework for enhancing seafarers' competence in energy-efficient ship operations," *Heliyon*, vol. 10, 17 Sep. 2024, ISSN: 24058440. DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e36505.
- [11] J. Jeon, P. Lee, and G. Theotokatos, "Autoship deliverable d7.2: Autonomous ships: Training framework for crew, operators and designers," AUTOSHIP Consortium, Tech. Rep., Dec. 2022.
- [12] V. Bolbot, G. Theotokatos, J. Faivre, and L. Wengersberg, "Autoship deliverable d2.4: Risk assessments, fail-safe procedures and acceptance criteria," AUTOSHIP consortiums, Tech. Rep., Nov. 2021.
- [13] SMI, *Being A Responsible Industry: Maritime Autonomous Ship Systems (MASS) UK Industry Conduct Principles and Guide to Best Practice*, 9th ed. Society of Maritime Industries, Nov. 2025.
- [14] IMO, "Interim guidelines for mass trials," MSC.1/Circ.1604, Jun. 2019.
- [15] E. Edwards, "Man and machine: Systems for safety," in *Proceedings of The BALPA Technical Symposium*, 1972.
- [16] UN, "The united nations convention on the law of the sea (unclos)," Dec. 1982. [Online]. Available: <https://www.unclos.org/>.